

RISK FACTORS OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY IN NEONATES

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Abstract

OBJECTIVES: To determine the risk associated with different maternal and neonatal variables in the evolution of acute kidney injury in newborns hospitalized in critical care.

STUDY DESIGN: Prospective cohort study.

SETTING/DURATION OF STUDY: Department of Pediatrics, Combined Military Hospital, Lahore, Aug 2022 to Aug 2024.

METHODOLOGY: We studied 100 neonates, of both genders, admitted for critical care in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit. Those neonates who were lost to follow-up, or those with congenital defects of the renal and urinary tract were excluded. All patients underwent monitoring for the development of AKI, which assessed according to the modified kidney disease: Improving Global Outcomes criteria for neonates. All patients were followed up till the end of the neonatal period.

RESULTS: Male gender (OR: 4.17, CI 95% 1.52 – 11.48, p=0.004), APGAR score at birth <8 (OR: 4.63, CI 95% 1.83 – 11.76, p<0.001), respiratory distress syndrome (OR: 42.78, CI 95% 5.18 – 353.42, p<0.001), surfactant therapy (OR: 4.81, CI 95% 1.68 – 13.76, p=0.002), requirement for mechanical ventilation (OR: 20.32, CI 95% 6.71 – 61.53, p<0.001) and a requirement for inotropic support (OR: 43.97, CI 95% 12.03 – 160.76, p<0.001) were all positively associated with the occurrence of AKI, while antenatal steroid exposure (OR: 0.33, CI 95% 0.14 – 0.812, p=0.014) appeared to be protective.

CONCLUSION: Acute kidney injury is associated with a number of maternal, neonatal, and pregnancy factors that can be used to identify pregnancies at risk.

INTRODUCTION

Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) is a dangerous complication affecting as many as a third of all neonates admitted to critical care units, with potentially severe implications for morbidity and mortality.¹ This population is particularly vulnerable to AKI, with the kidneys undergoing substantial changes throughout intrauterine life

and at delivery, due to physiological immaturity and increased susceptibility to various insults.²

The etiology of AKI in neonates is multifactorial, encompassing a wide array of maternal and neonatal factors. Maternal factors such as maternal age, comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, diabetes), and pregnancy-related complications (e.g.,

pre-eclampsia, placental insufficiency) can influence fetal development and predispose neonates to AKI.³ Maternal factors may directly impact fetal renal function through altered placental perfusion and subsequent fetal hypoxia or indirectly through the transmission of maternal diseases or medications to the fetus.^{4,5} Neonatal variables including gestational age, birth weight, and perinatal factors such as birth asphyxia, sepsis, and respiratory distress syndrome are also implicated in the pathogenesis of neonatal AKI.⁶ Prematurity and low birth weight are well-established risk factors for AKI due to the immaturity of the neonatal kidney and susceptibility to hemodynamic instability and nephrotoxic insults.⁷ Birth asphyxia and hypoxic-ischemic injury can lead to renal hypoperfusion and ischemic AKI, further exacerbating the vulnerability of neonatal kidneys.^{7,8} Furthermore, critical care interventions commonly employed in neonatal units such as mechanical ventilation, administration of nephrotoxic medications, and fluid management strategies can contribute to the development of AKI.⁹ Drugs such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), aminoglycosides and contrast agents are known nephrotoxins that can adversely affect renal function in neonates.⁹ Additionally, the delicate fluid and electrolyte balance in neonates requires meticulous monitoring and management to prevent volume overload or dehydration, both of which can precipitate AKI.¹⁰

Despite advancements in neonatal critical care, the incidence of AKI in remains significant in this population, necessitating further exploration of its risk factors for targeted preventive strategies and interventions, particularly in Pakistani healthcare setups. The current study aims to fill this gap by comprehensively analyzing the association between maternal and neonatal variables and the risk of AKI development in neonates hospitalized in critical care. By elucidating these risk factors, we strive to enhance our understanding of neonatal AKI pathophysiology and ultimately improve the management and outcomes of this vulnerable population.

METHODOLOGY

This was a prospective study conducted between Aug 2022 to Aug 2024 in the Department of Paediatrics, Combined Military Hospital, Lahore on 100 neonates admitted for critical care in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). Prior to

study participation, we secured informed consent from the parents or legal guardians of every child involved. The research protocol was planned in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki and local institutional ethical guidelines. Participants was selected via consecutive, non-probability sampling. The EPI tools sample size calculator was used to calculate the sample size keeping power of the study of 95%, a confidence level of 95%, an assumed odds ratio of 12.09, and an expected proportion in controls of 0.202, which were the odds ratio of neonates born before the completion of 32 weeks of gestation for the development of AKI and the proportion of neonates born after the completion of 32 weeks of gestation who developed AKI, respectively, from Mazaheri et al.¹¹

Inclusion Criteria: All neonates of both genders admitted to the NICU were included for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Those neonates who were lost to follow-up, or those with congenital abnormalities of the renal and urinary tract were excluded from analysis.

All study enrollees were underwent recording of demographic and gestational data and a thorough history was noted, along with a detailed clinical examination. All patients underwent peripheral blood sampling of approximately 1 mL daily which was used to assess serum creatinine levels, for the development of AKI. The sampling itself was conducted by a trained paediatric phlebotomist with a minimum of two years experience in neonatal blood sampling. The testing was continued till discharge of the patient from the NICU. AKI was defined according to the modified Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) criteria for neonates.¹²

Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (Version 27, IBM Corp; Armonk, USA). Mean and SD was calculated for quantitative variables specifically patient age, gestational age at birth, birth-weight, APGAR score at birth, and length of NICU stay. Qualitative variables like gender, mode of delivery, multiple gestation, maternal comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, hypertension), presence of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS)/sepsis, whether surfactant treatment or steroids were given, requirement for mechanical ventilation or inotropic support and occurrence of AKI were displayed as frequency and percentage. Study participants were grouped according to whether AKI developed or not.

Categorical data was compared between the two groups using the Chi Square test/Fischer Exact test, while continuous variables were compared using the independent samples *t* test/Mann-Whitney U test. Normality of the data was measured with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Throughout the study, a *p* value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. Odds ratios were calculated for different variables for the occurrence of AKI.

RESULTS

The research sample for this study was based on 100 neonates admitted to the NICU. The median age of the study sample upon inclusion in the study was 6.00 (IQR: 9.00) days, of whom 57 (57.0%) were males. Nineteen (19.0%) mothers suffered from diabetes mellitus during gestation, while 12 (12.0%) suffered from hypertension during the same period. Only 1 (1.0%) pregnancy was multiple gestation. The median gestational age

at the time of delivery was 36.00 (IQR: 5.00) weeks. A total of 57 (57.0%) patients were given antenatal steroids. Vaginal deliveries were performed in 68 (68.0%) cases, while 32 (32.0%) cases were delivered by caesarean section. The median birth-weight was 2430.00 (IQR: 857.00) g, while the median APGAR score at 0 minutes was 8.00 (IQR: 2.00). RDS was present in 12 (12.0%) patients, while 20 (20.0%) suffered from sepsis. Surfactant was administered to 19 (19.0%) patients, 27 (27.0%) required mechanical ventilation, while 25 (25.0%) required inotropic support. The median length of NICU stay was 7.00 (IQR: 10.00) days. A total of 29 (29.0%) patients developed AKI during the course of hospital admission. Table-I shows the patient characteristics/study outcomes distributed according to the development of AKI.

Table-I. Patient characteristics/study outcomes according to AKI development (n=100)

Variable	AKI Present (n=29)	AKI Absent (n=71)	<i>p</i> value
Age (days)	8.00 (IQR: 9.00)	6.00 (IQR: 6.00)	0.207
Gender			
Male	23 (79.3%)	34 (47.9%)	0.004
Female	6 (20.7%)	37 (52.1%)	
Maternal diabetes mellitus	9 (31.0%)	10 (14.1%)	0.050
Maternal hypertension	3 (10.3%)	9 (12.7%)	1.000
Multiple gestation	1 (3.4%)	-	0.290
Gestational age at birth (weeks)	33.00 (IQR: 5.00)	36.00 (IQR: 4.00)	<0.001
Antenatal steroid exposure	11 (37.9%)	46 (64.8%)	0.014
Mode of Delivery			
Vaginal Delivery	20 (68.9%)	48 (67.6%)	0.895
Caesarean section	9 (31.1%)	23 (32.4%)	
Birth-weight (g)	2258 (IQR: 645)	2501 (IQR: 923)	0.043
APGAR score at birth	7.00 (IQR: 2.00)	8.00 (IQR: 2.00)	<0.001

Respiratory distress syndrome	11 (37.9%)	1 (1.4%)	<0.001
Sepsis	10 (34.5%)	10 (14.1%)	0.021
Surfactant therapy	11 (37.9%)	8 (11.3%)	0.002
Mechanical ventilation	20 (68.9%)	7 (9.9%)	<0.001
Inotropic support	21 (72.4%)	4 (5.6%)	<0.001
Length of hospital stay (days)	8.00 (IQR: 12.00)	7.00 (IQR: 10.00)	0.544

Table-II shows the odds ratios/risk for studied variables with the development of AKI. Male gender (OR: 4.17, CI 95% 1.52 - 11.48, $p=0.004$), maternal diabetes mellitus (OR: 2.75, CI 95% 0.98 - 7.71, $p=0.050$), gestational age <37 weeks at birth (OR: 2.89, CI 95% 1.10 - 7.62, $p=0.028$), APGAR score at birth <8 (OR: 4.63, CI 95% 1.83 - 11.76, $p<0.001$), respiratory distress syndrome (OR: 42.78, CI 95% 5.18 - 353.42, $p<0.001$), sepsis (OR: 3.21, CI 95% 1.16 - 8.87, $p=0.021$),

surfactant therapy (OR: 4.81, CI 95% 1.68 - 13.76, $p=0.002$), requirement for mechanical ventilation (OR: 20.32, CI 95% 6.71 - 61.53, $p<0.001$) and a requirement for inotropic support (OR: 43.97, CI 95% 12.03 - 160.76, $p<0.001$) were all positively associated with the occurrence of AKI, while antenatal steroid exposure (OR: 0.33, CI 95% 0.14 - 0.812, $p=0.014$) appeared to be protective.

Table-II. Odds ratio of different variables for the occurrence of AKI (n=100)

Variable	Odds Ratio, p -value
Age <7 days	0.51 (CI 95% 0.21 - 1.26), $p=0.144$
Male gender	4.17 (CI 95% 1.52 - 11.48), $p=0.004$
Maternal diabetes mellitus	2.75 (CI 95% 0.98 - 7.71), $p=0.050$
Maternal hypertension	0.80 (CI 95% 0.20 - 3.17), $p=1.000$
Multiple gestation	3.53 (CI 95% 2.58 - 4.84), $p=0.290$
Gestational age <37 weeks	2.89 (CI 95% 1.10 - 7.62), $p=0.028$
Antenatal steroid exposure	0.33 (CI 95% 0.14 - 0.812), $p=0.014$
Caesarean section	0.94 (CI 95% 0.37 - 2.38), $p=0.895$
Birth-weight <2500 g	1.95 (CI 95% 0.80 - 4.79), $p=0.140$
APGAR score at birth <8	4.63 (CI 95% 1.83 - 11.76), $p<0.001$
Respiratory distress syndrome	42.78 (CI 95% 5.18 - 353.42), $p<0.001$
Sepsis	3.21 (CI 95% 1.16 - 8.87), $p=0.021$
Surfactant therapy	4.81 (CI 95% 1.68 - 13.76), $p=0.002$

Mechanical ventilation	20.32 (CI 95% 6.71 - 61.53), $p < 0.001$
Inotropic support	43.97 (CI 95% 12.03 - 160.76), $p < 0.001$

DISCUSSION

This prospective cohort study was designed to determine the risk factors for AKI in neonates admitted to the NICU. Our findings underscore the multifactorial nature of AKI in this vulnerable population, revealing several significant associations with clinical and demographic variables.

One of the key findings of our study was the strong association between male gender and the development of AKI, with males having more than four times the odds of developing AKI compared to females. Ustun et al also reported that male neonates had an increased risk for the development of AKI (OR: 3.43, CI 95% 1.03 - 11.48, $p = 0.04$),¹³ a conclusion that was also shared by Munyendo et al, who reported that male neonates had a higher frequency of incidence of AKI, when compared to females, with an incidence ratio of 4:3.¹⁴ This gender disparity may be attributed to intrinsic biological differences in renal development and susceptibility to renal insults between male and female neonates, however, this aspect of our study requires further research.

Maternal diabetes mellitus during gestation was another significant risk factor associated with AKI, in our study. We postulate that the hyperglycaemic intrauterine environment may adversely affect fetal kidney development, predisposing neonates to renal complications post-birth. However, previous studies conducted on the topic, such as by AlGadeeb et al who determined that maternal diabetes mellitus is not connected to the evolution of neonatal AKI, ($p = 0.370$).¹⁵ We believe this difference in results may be due to two reasons: 1) the degree of glycaemic control may have resulted in significant confounding in results, and 2) high blood sugar is connected with a substantial rise in the occurrence of RDS and premature birth which, in themselves, may be associated with an increased risk for the development of AKI,^{16,17} thus, the relationship between maternal diabetes mellitus and neonatal AKI may be an indirect one.

The current study showed that neonates born before completion of 37 weeks gestation i.e., those born premature, had an almost three times the increase in risk of developing AKI, which is in

congruence with other studies on the subject such as Shalaby et al ($p < 0.001$),¹⁸ and Mazaheri et al (OR: 12.09, CI 95% 3.51 - 41.63, $p < 0.001$).¹¹ Prematurity is a well-known risk factor for various neonatal complications, including AKI, due to the immaturity of renal structures and function.

Notably, a low APGAR score at birth (< 8) was a significant predictor of AKI in the present study. Ustun et al also determined that both one minute and five minute APGAR scores were associated with the development of neonatal AKI (OR: 1.52, CI 95% 1.03 - 2.23, $p = 0.030$ and OR: 1.79, CI 95% 1.13 - 2.84, $p = 0.010$, respectively),¹³ a finding that was agreed with by Mazaheri et al.¹¹ This finding suggests that neonates who experience perinatal distress or asphyxia are at a heightened risk for renal injury, likely due to hypoxic-ischemic damage to the kidneys. Similarly, RDS was seen to be connected with AKI in our study, highlighting the critical interplay between respiratory and renal function in neonates, an issue that has been previously highlighted in other studies on this topic such as Kaushik et al and El-Kalioby et al.^{19,20}

The necessity for mechanical ventilation, and inotropic support were also strongly associated with AKI, in our study. AlGadeeb et al also reported that patients who required mechanical ventilation ($p < 0.001$) or inotropic support ($p < 0.001$) had a significantly increased frequency of AKI.¹⁵ These interventions, often markers of severe illness, likely indicate that neonates requiring extensive respiratory or cardiovascular support are at substantial risk for developing renal complications, rather than the interventions themselves being associated with direct renal injury. Sepsis emerged as another significant risk factor in the current study. Sepsis in neonates can lead to systemic inflammation and multi-organ dysfunction, including the kidneys. Mazaheri et al also reported that sepsis was associated with AKI in neonates ($p < 0.05$),¹¹ a conclusion that was shared by AlGadeeb et al ($p < 0.001$).¹⁵

Interestingly, antenatal steroid exposure was found to have a protective effect against the development of AKI in our study, a fact which was also reported by AlGadeeb et al ($p < 0.001$) on univariate

analysis.¹⁵ Antenatal steroids are administered to enhance foetal lung maturity in cases of anticipated preterm delivery and may have beneficial effects on renal development and function, potentially reducing the risk of AKI, however, this aspect of our research further study before our conclusions can be said to be concrete.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

The number of patients in our study was relatively small, which may limit the ability of our findings to be generalized to other populations. The observational nature of the study precludes establishing causality, and despite adjusting for various potential confounders, residual confounding cannot be entirely ruled out. Additionally, the diagnosis of AKI was based on one particular clinical/lab criteria, which might introduce some variability in the identification and classification of AKI cases. The single-center design may also limit the applicability of the results to other settings with different patient populations and care practices. More studies with larger cohorts across multiple healthcare centers are required to validate and extend these findings.

CONCLUSION

This study identified several significant risk factors for AKI in neonates admitted to the NICU, including male gender, maternal diabetes mellitus, preterm birth, low APGAR scores, respiratory distress syndrome, sepsis, and the need for intensive respiratory and cardiovascular support. The protective effect of antenatal steroid exposure against AKI also highlights a potential intervention point. These findings emphasize the importance of close monitoring and early identification of at-risk neonates to prevent and manage AKI effectively, thereby improving neonatal outcomes. Future research should focus on elucidating the underlying mechanisms and exploring targeted interventions to mitigate these risks.

REFERENCES

Roy JP, Goldstein SL, Schuh MP. Under-Recognition of Neonatal Acute Kidney Injury and Lack of Follow-Up. *Am J Perinatol*. 2022 Apr;39(5):526-531. doi: 10.1055/s-0040-1716841.

Fang CC, Huang SH, Kuo CW, Chwo MJ. Acute Kidney Injury in Newborns. *Hu Li Za Zhi*. 2019 Dec;66(6):66-73. Chinese. doi: 10.6224/JN.201912_66(6).09.

DeFreitas MJ, Griffin R, Sanderson K, Nada A, Charlton JR, Jetton JG, et al; Neonatal Kidney Collaborative; University of Alabama, Birmingham; Cincinnati Children's Hospital; Canberra Hospital; (currently at the University of Rochester); Children's Hospital of Colorado; (currently Cincinnati Children's Hospital, Cincinnati, OH); Children's Hospital at Montefiore/Albert Einstein; Children's National Medical Center; Golisano Children's Hospital University of Rochester; (currently Union Hospital, Terre Haute); Maimonides Medical Center; McGill University; Medanta, Medicity The Cradle; Metrohealth Medical Center; Nationwide Children's Hospital; Stony Brook University; Texas Children's Hospital; Tufts Medical Center; University of British Columbia; University of Iowa; Patrick Brophy (currently University of Rochester); University of Kentucky; University of Miami; University of Michigan; (currently Medical University of South Carolina); University of New Mexico; (currently Texas Children's Hospital); (currently University of Utah); University of Virginia; (currently University of Wisconsin); University of Washington. Maternal Hypertension Disorders and Neonatal Acute Kidney Injury: Results from the AWAKEN Study. *Am J Perinatol*. 2024 Apr;41(5):649-659. doi: 10.1055/a-1780-2249.

Szczepanski J, Griffin A, Novotny S, Wallace K. Acute Kidney Injury in Pregnancies Complicated With Preeclampsia or HELLP Syndrome. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2020 Feb 7;7:22. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2020.00022.

Sharma M, Mazumder MA, Alam S, Deka N, Shehwar D, Mahanta PJ, et al. Characteristics, maternal and neonatal outcomes of acute kidney injury in preeclampsia: A prospective, single-center study. *Clin Nephrol*. 2021 Nov;96(5):263-269. doi: 10.5414/CN110447.

Momtaz HE, Sabzehei MK, Rasuli B, Torabian S. The main etiologies of acute kidney injury in the newborns hospitalized in the neonatal intensive care unit. *J Clin Neonatol*. 2014 Apr;3(2):99-102. doi: 10.4103/2249-4847.134691.

- Perico N, Askenazi D, Cortinovis M, Remuzzi G. Maternal and environmental risk factors for neonatal AKI and its long-term consequences. *Nat Rev Nephrol.* 2018 Nov;14(11):688-703. doi: 10.1038/s41581-018-0054-y.
- Mota-Rojas D, Villanueva-García D, Solimano A, Muns R, Ibarra-Ríos D, Mota-Reyes A. Pathophysiology of Perinatal Asphyxia in Humans and Animal Models. *Biomedicines.* 2022 Feb 1;10(2):347. doi: 10.3390/biomedicines10020347.
- Alhassani RY, Bagadood RM, Balubaid RN, Barno HI, Alahmadi MO, Ayoub NA. Drug Therapies Affecting Renal Function: An Overview. *Cureus.* 2021 Nov 26;13(11):e19924. doi: 10.7759/cureus.19924.
- Branagan A, Costigan CS, Stack M, Slagle C, Molloy EJ. Management of Acute Kidney Injury in Extremely Low Birth Weight Infants. *Front Pediatr.* 2022 Mar 30;10:867715. doi: 10.3389/fped.2022.867715.
- Mazaheri M, Rambod M. Risk factors analysis for acute kidney injury in the newborn infants: predictive strategies. *Iran J Kidney Dis.* 2019 Sep;13(5):310-315.
- Coleman C, Tambay Perez A, Selewski DT, Steflik HJ. Neonatal Acute Kidney Injury. *Front Pediatr.* 2022 Apr 7;10:842544. doi: 10.3389/fped.2022.842544.
- Ustun N, Ovali F. Risk Factors and Outcomes of Acute Kidney Injury in Neonates with Persistent Pulmonary Hypertension of the Newborn. *Medeni Med J.* 2021;36(3):193-200. doi: 10.5222/MMJ.2021.22687.
- Munyendo C, Admani B, Mburugu P, Simba J, Lusweti B, Gachara N, et al. Prevalence of acute kidney injury and its characteristics among neonates with suspected sepsis in a tertiary hospital in Kenya. *Afr Health Sci.* 2023 Mar;23(1):704-710. doi: 10.4314/ahs.v23i1.75.
- AlGadeeb K, Qaraqei M, Algadeeb R, Faqehi H, Al-Matary A. Prediction of risk factors and outcomes of neonatal acute kidney injury. *J Nephrol.* 2021 Oct;34(5):1659-1668. doi: 10.1007/s40620-021-01130-x.
- Li Y, Wang W, Zhang D. Maternal diabetes mellitus and risk of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome: a meta-analysis. *Acta Diabetol.* 2019 Jul;56(7):729-740. doi: 10.1007/s00592-019-01327-4.
- Muche AA, Olayemi OO, Gete YK. Gestational diabetes mellitus increased the risk of adverse neonatal outcomes: A prospective cohort study in Northwest Ethiopia. *Midwifery.* 2020 Aug;87:102713. doi: 10.1016/j.midw.2020.102713.
- Shalaby MA, Sawan ZA, Nawawi E, Alsaedi S, Al-Wassia H, Kari JA. Incidence, risk factors, and outcome of neonatal acute kidney injury: a prospective cohort study. *Pediatr Nephrol.* 2018 Sep;33(9):1617-1624. doi: 10.1007/s00467-018-3966-7.
- Kaushik S, Villacres S, Eisenberg R, Medar SS. Acute Kidney Injury in Pediatric Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *J Intensive Care Med.* 2021 Sep;36(9):1084-1090. Doi: 10.1177/0885066620944042.
- El-Kalioby M, Khashana A, Kamel N, Hennawi S. Causes of Neonatal Acute Renal Injury during Critical Illnesses. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl.* 2022 May-Jun;33(3):418-424. doi: 10.4103/1319-2442.385965.

